

The Effect of Spiritual Prayer Guidance on Anxiety Levels in Pre-Operative Patients

Putri Cintya Dewi¹, Imam Subekti²

^{1,2}Prodi Sarjana Terapan Keperawatan Malang Politeknik Kesehatan Kemenkes Malang

ABSTRACT: Surgery is an invasive medical procedure. Before surgery, patients experience anxiety. If anxiety is not addressed, it can delay the operation by increasing blood pressure. One nursing intervention to prevent anxiety is through spiritual prayer guidance. The purpose of this study was to determine the effect of spiritual prayer guidance on the level of anxiety in pre-operative patients. The research method used a quantitative research type, a pre-experimental research design (pre-test and post-test one group design). The sample of pre-operative patients at RSI Aisyiyah Malang in March-April 2025 amounted to 100 respondents. The instrument for measuring anxiety levels used the Amsterdam Pre-Operative Anxiety and Informational Scale questionnaire. The results showed that before the intervention, 7% of respondents experienced mild anxiety and 93% experienced moderate anxiety. After receiving the spiritual prayer mentoring intervention, 6% of respondents experienced no anxiety, 92% experienced mild anxiety, and 2% experienced moderate anxiety. The Wilcoxon test analysis showed a p-value (Sig. 2-tailed) of 0.000 ($p < 0.05$), thus H_0 was rejected and H_1 was accepted. This means there was a significant difference in anxiety levels before and after the spiritual prayer mentoring treatment in preoperative patients at RSI Aisyiyah Malang. The conclusion of this study indicates that spiritual prayer mentoring is effective in reducing anxiety levels in preoperative patients. It is hoped that nurses, as educators, can implement spiritual prayer mentoring to address preoperative anxiety.

KEYWORDS: Preoperative Anxiety, Spiritual Prayer Mentoring

INTRODUCTION

Surgery is an invasive medical procedure performed to diagnose or treat various diseases, injuries, or abnormalities in the body. The surgical process can cause tissue injury, which then triggers physiological changes in the body and can impact other organs. 1. Before undergoing surgery, many patients experience anxiety problems which are common emotional reactions, especially because the surgical experience is new for them. 2.

Preoperative anxiety is a serious problem faced by patients. Researchers found that spiritual support is not optimal. If anxiety is not addressed, it can hinder the surgical process by increasing heart rate and blood pressure.

According to the World Health Organization (WHO, 2020), a total of 534 million people experienced anxiety before surgery in 2018. In Indonesia, the number of people undergoing surgical procedures in 2020 reached 1.2 million. According to information from the Basic Health Research (Riskesdas) (2020), the number of patients undergoing surgery in East Java reached 41,285. Interviews with relevant parties at Aisyiyah Islamic Hospital in Malang revealed that many patients, an estimated 80%, experienced anxiety before surgery.

Look at the physical symptoms that arise. For some patients, undergoing surgery is a stressful experience, creating fear of anesthesia, pain, or even death. All of these are responses to situations perceived as threatening. 4

The impact on patients undergoing surgery can affect various aspects, including difficulty concentrating, confusion, anxiety, and feelings of unease. Increased blood pressure, tremors, and a high heart rate can hinder the smooth operation. For example, increased blood pressure due to anxiety can interfere with the surgical procedure. Therefore, it is crucial to provide appropriate preoperative anxiety management for patients, both by the patient and the nurse. 5

Anxiety management can be pharmacological, namely through the administration of medication, or non-pharmacological, which includes distraction techniques, spiritual healing, prayer, humor, and relaxation therapy (Prasetyo et al., 2023). One nursing intervention to prevent anxiety is through spiritual therapy. The main goal of this therapy is to build self-confidence, which is crucial in the healing process, in addition to the use of medications and medical procedures. 6

Spiritual care for pre-operative patients is a procedure aimed at addressing anxiety, with the goal of improving the patient's emotional intelligence. This can help patients implement effective coping strategies to reduce the intensity of their anxiety. Prayer, as a form of worship, has no strict requirements or pillars.

The Effect of Spiritual Prayer Guidance on Anxiety Levels in Pre-Operative Patients

As nurses, we can act as educators who can help patients calm their hearts through prayer, which can be one way to reduce anxiety. As nurses, we can provide spiritual support through prayer. Based on this background, the research question is: What is the effect of spiritual support through prayer on anxiety levels in preoperative patients in the Central Surgical Installation preparation room at RSI Aisyiyah Malang? This study aims to determine the effect of spiritual support through prayer on anxiety levels in preoperative patients in the Central Surgical Installation preparation room at RSI Aisyiyah Malang.

Sebagai perawat mampu berperan sebagai edukator yang dapat membantu pasien menenangkan hati dengan berdoa agar menjadi salah satu usaha untuk mengurangi ansietas. Sebagai perawat pelaksana dapat memberikan pendampingan spiritual berupa doa.

METHODS

This was a quantitative study with a pre-experimental design (one-group pre-post-test design). The sample consisted of 100 pre-operative patients at RSI Aisyiyah Malang in March-April 2025. Data collection methods included interviews and the Amsterdam Pre-Operative Anxiety and Informational Scale (APAIS) questionnaire. Data analysis used the Wilcoxon test to analyze differences in anxiety before and after the intervention. This study received ethical approval from the Health Research Ethics Committee (KEPK) of the Ministry of Health Polytechnic of Malang in December 2025, in accordance with applicable regulations, as outlined in document No. DP.04.03/F.XXI.30/00246/2025, for the purpose of research feasibility.

RESULT

Respondent Characteristics

The general description of the respondents in this study includes the characteristics of the respondents, namely pre-operative patients at Aisyiyah Hospital Malang, out of a total of 100 respondents.

Table 1. Distribution of Respondent Characteristics

Variabel	Category	Frequency	Percent
Age	18 -25 year old	17	17,0
	26 -35 year old	22	22,0
	36-45 year old	20	20,0
	46 tahun-60 tahun	41	41,0
	Totaly	100	100,0
Gender	Male	41	41,0
	Female	59	59,0
	Totaly	100	100,0
Last education	YHS	4	4,0
	SHS	51	51,0
	Bachelor	45	45,0
	Totaly	100	100,0
Level of Surgery	Minor Surgery	57	57,0
	Majory Surgery	43	43,0
	Totaly	100	100,0
Surgery	Digestive	10	10,0
	Onkology	40	40,0
	Urology	18	18,0
	Orthopedy	3	3,0
	Eye	11	11,0
	TKV	5	5,0
	Obgyn	13	13,0
	Total	100	100,0

The characteristics of pre-operative patient respondents at RSI Aisyiyah Malang in March-April 2025 were almost half (41%) aged 46-60 years, most (59%) were female, most (51%) had a high school education, most (57%) underwent minor surgery, and almost half (40%) underwent oncology surgery.

The Effect of Spiritual Prayer Guidance on Anxiety Levels in Pre-Operative Patients

2. Patient Anxiety Levels Before Intervention

Table 2. Distribution of Pre-Intervention Anxiety Levels

	Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent
Mild Anxiety	7	7,0	7,0
Moderate Anxiety	93	93,0	93,0
Total	100	100,0	100,0

The level of anxiety of pre-operative patients at RSI Aisyiyah Malang before being given intervention was mild anxiety in 7 people (7%) and moderate anxiety in 93 people (93%).

2. Patient Anxiety Levels Post-Intervention

Table3. Distribution of Post-Intervention Anxiety Levels

	Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent
Not Anxiety/Normaly	6	6,0	6,0
Mild Anxiety	92	92,0	92,0
Moderate Anxiety	2	2,0	2,0
Total	100	100,0	100,0

The level of anxiety of pre-operative patients at RSI Aisyiyah Malang after being given intervention with a normal level of anxiety or no anxiety was 6 people (6%), mild anxiety was 92 people (92%) and moderate anxiety was 2 people (2%).

2. Differences in Anxiety Pre- and Post-Intervention

Table 4. Differences in Anxiety Pre- and Post-Intervention

	N	Mean Rank	Sum of Ranks
Negative Ranks	96a	48,50	4656,00
Positive Ranks	0b	,00	,00
Ties	4c		
Totally	100		

Table 5. Results of the Wilcoxon Test for Differences in Anxiety Post-Test of Spiritual Prayer Assistance Intervention

Z	-9,749b
Asymp. Sig. (2-tailed)	,000

Based on the table above, the significance value (Asymp. Sig (2-tailed)) is 0.000. Because the Asymp. Sig (2-tailed) value is smaller than the specified significance level or <0.05 , H_0 is rejected and H_1 is accepted, which means that there is a difference in the level of anxiety before and after the spiritual prayer assistance treatment in pre-operative patients at RSI Aisyiyah Malang. The result of the Z value = -9.749. shows a very significant level of difference between the level of anxiety before and after the intervention.

DISCUSSION

In this study, one of the stressors experienced by respondents was the upcoming surgery (pre-operative). Pre-operative anxiety is caused by factors that patients may not necessarily experience in the operating room, such as: pain, physical changes, the threat to life due to the surgical procedure, fear of unconsciousness after anesthesia, fear of the operation not going smoothly, and fear of disability or complications during the operation, thus becoming a burden on the family.¹¹

According to the researchers' assumptions, patients undergoing surgery tend to experience anxiety, whether mild, moderate, or severe, in response to uncertainty and fear regarding the medical procedure, the surgical outcome, and the recovery process.

The study's findings align with those of Sanjaya et al. (2022) in the central surgical unit at Dr. Soedarso Regional Hospital. The majority of respondents who underwent the intervention reported post-intervention changes, feeling more confident, optimistic, calm, and accepting of reality.

The Effect of Spiritual Prayer Guidance on Anxiety Levels in Pre-Operative Patients

Spiritual support therapy through prayer is a form of alternative medicine that utilizes a religious approach. This approach utilizes prayer as a psychological therapy. The goal is to increase optimism and self-confidence, which are crucial, in addition to medication and medical procedures.

Thus, researchers believe that spiritual support through prayer has the potential to be an effective way to reduce anxiety levels and improve an individual's mental well-being. Spiritual support through prayer can reduce anxiety levels and strengthen supportive cognitive aspects.

Similar research results were obtained by Suyanto et al. (2023) at Jombang Regional General Hospital, showing that out of 22 respondents, 19 showed a decrease in anxiety levels after receiving spiritual therapy intervention through guided prayer before surgery. Statistical analysis using the Wilcoxon test showed a p-value of 0.000 ($p < 0.05$), indicating a difference in anxiety levels between the pre-test and post-test groups.

Spiritual support services for patients undergoing surgery are a form of spiritual care aimed at patients experiencing anxiety. The goal is to improve patients' emotional intelligence, enabling them to understand their circumstances, surrender to God, and recognize that every event in life is a gift from God. Thus, clients can improve their coping skills, which can reduce anxiety levels.¹²

Understanding spiritual support through prayer has shown that it can become a habit that can be practiced during times of anxiety. Continuous prayer influences an individual's mindset, changing daily behavior and habits to become calmer.

After receiving intervention in the form of spiritual support through prayer, patients become more confident and experience less anxiety or worry. Patients who initially felt excessive worry and anxiety gradually begin to calm down and accept their current situation. Spiritual support in the form of healing prayers can influence negative thoughts or fears, making them confident and less anxious during surgery.

Researchers hypothesize that spiritual support through prayer can provide psychological and emotional calming effects for patients undergoing surgery. In this study, the highest score for question 4 (I'm afraid of surgery) decreased by 57 points, likely due to the fact that patients had never had surgery before. Meanwhile, the lowest score for question 3 (I want to know as much as possible about anesthesia) decreased by 74 points, likely due to factors such as education level and the type of surgery that influence pre-operative anxiety levels.

Prayer is believed to reduce anxiety levels by increasing self-confidence, inner peace, and belief in a protective force. Therefore, patients receiving spiritual support are expected to show a significant reduction in anxiety levels compared to those before receiving the intervention.

CONCLUSION

The spiritual support and prayer intervention for pre-operative patients at RSI Aisyiyah Malang has shown significant results, demonstrating a difference in pre- and post-test anxiety levels. Spiritual support therapy in the form of prayer is a religious approach through prayer, which is a healing element for illness or a psychotherapeutic approach aimed at fostering self-confidence and optimism for healing from God Almighty. Therefore, it is hoped that this intervention can serve as a reference for implementing spiritual support and prayer for every patient undergoing surgical procedures at the hospital.

REFERNCES

- 1) Rismawan W.(2019). Tingkat Kecemasan Pasien Pre-Operasi Di Rsud Dr.Soekardjo Kota Tasikmalaya. Jurnal Kesehatan Bakti Tunas Husada, Jurnal Ilmu-ilmu Keperawatan, Analis Kesehatan dan Farmasi. 2019; Vol. 19(1):65-70. doi:10.36465/jkbth.v19i1.451
- 2) Moonti MA. (2023). Efektivitas support system keluarga terhadap penurunan tingkat kecemasan pasien pre operatif di ruang bedah RSUD Gunung Jati Cirebon. Journal Nurs Practice Education. Vol;3(2):112-118. doi:10.34305/jnpe.v3i2.656
- 3) Arifin Noor, dkk. (2023) Pengaruh Pendidikan Kesehatan Dengan Media Video Edukasi Terhadap Tingkat Kecemasan Pada Pasien Pre Operasi Fraktur. Jurnal Ilmu Kedokteran dan Kesehatan. Vol ;2(2):01-13. doi:10.55606/klinik.v2i2.1206
- 4) Rahmayati E, dkk. (2018). . Pengaruh Dukungan Spritual terhadap Tingkat Kecemasan pada Pasien Pre-Operasi. Jurnal Kesehatan. Vol;9(1):138-142. doi:10.26630/jk.v9i1.778
- 5) Anwar HA, dkk (2024). Hubungan Usia dengan Tingkat Kecemasan pada Pasien Bedah Elektif Dewasa. Jurnal Keperawatan Terapan Poltekkes Kemenkes Malang. Vol ;09(01):28-36. <https://doi.org/10.36916/jk>
- 6) Gumilang NM, Susanto A, Suryani RL (2022). Hubungan Antara Jenis Kelamin dan Usia dengan Tingkat Kecemasan Pasien Pre Operasi dengan Anestesi Spinal di RS Khusus Bedah Jatiwinangun Purwokerto. Jurnal Nasional Penelitian dan Pengabdian Masyarakat. Vol 2;I:332-337.

The Effect of Spiritual Prayer Guidance on Anxiety Levels in Pre-Operative Patients

- 7) Sari Yuli permata, Riasmini N, Guslinda. (2020). Analisis Faktor-faktor yang Berhubungan dengan Tingkat Kecemasan pada Pasien Preoperasi Bedah Mayor di Ruang Teratai. *Jurnal Menara Ilmu UMSB*..Vol;XIV(02):133-147. <https://jurnal.umsb.ac.id/index.php/menarailmu/article/view/2176/1797>
- 8) Ahsan, Lestari R, Sriati (2017). Faktor-Faktor Yang Mempengaruhi Kecemasan Pre Operasi Pada Pasien Sectio Caesarea Di Ruang Instalasi Bedah Sentral Rsud Kanjuruhan Kepanjen Kabupaten Malang. *Jurnal Keperawatan. Dan Kesehatan* Vol;8(1):1-12.
- 9) Sanjaya TI, Hastuti L, Wahyuni T.(2019). Pengaruh Bimbingan Spiritual Terhadap Tingkat Bedah Sentral. *Jurnal Keperawatan dan Kesehatan*. 2022;13(1):29-34.
- 10) Islamiyyah U.(2022) Pengaruh Terapi Spiritual Terhadap Tingkat Kecemasan Pasien Pre Operasi : Literature Review . Published online. <http://digilib.unisayogya.ac.id/6432/1/UmiiyyatulIslamiyyah.pdf>
- 11) Suyanto, Indri, Taufiqurrahman.(2023) Pengaruh Terapi Spiritual Bimbingan Do'a Terhadap Tingkat Kecemasan Pasien Pre Operasi Dengan Spinal Anestesi. *Jurnal Ilmu Kesehatan dan Gizi*. Vol;1(2):245-256.
- 12) Hasniah, Siti Hamidah, Munazar CM.(2021). Hubungan Pendampingan Perawat Dengan Layanan Spiritual: Doa Dan Tawakkal Terhadap Tingkat Kecemasan Pasien Pre Operasi Fraktur Tertutup Di Rumah Sakit Meuraxa Kota Banda Aceh. *Jurnal Ilmu Kesehatan*. Vol;2(1):41-55.
- 13) Hafidz N, Rachmy RD. (2021) Mengasah Kecerdasan Spiritual Melalui Aktivitas Berdoa . *Ideas J Pendidikan, Sos dan Budaya*. Vol;7(4):59. doi:10.32884/ideas.v7i4.444